

INFLUENCE OF INSTRUCTIONAL SUPERVISION ON CURRICULUM IMPLEMENTATION IN SELECTED NORTH RIFT, KENYA COUNTIES PUBLIC SECONDARY SCHOOLS

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Abstract:

The aim of this paper is to describe how instructional supervision activities influenced curriculum implementation in selected North Rift counties public secondary schools in Kenya. Key educational stakeholders in the region are concerned with deteriorating quality education and that is why the study determined how internal quality assurance and standards of instructional supervision was carried out in the schools. This study was conducted in three counties in Kenya; Elgeyo-Marakwet, West Pokot and Baringo Counties. The paper adopted a descriptive survey research design targeting teachers, principals and sub counties quality assurance and standards officers. The study used questionnaire and interview schedule as instruments of data collection. Data analysis was done using descriptive and inferential statistics. Qualitative data analysis was done using thematic method. Research findings showed that instructional supervision had a significant influence ($\beta=0.203$ and $p=0.05$) on curriculum implementation in schools. the paper recommends that there is need for principals to continuously work with teachers on how to improve and revolutionise their teaching and learning approaches to match with the current and global trends in the teaching profession.

Keywords: supervision, instructional, curriculum, implementation

1. Introduction

Curriculum implementation involves day to day activities which school management and classroom teachers undertake in the pursuit of the objective of any given curriculum (Obanya, 2004). Ahmadi and Lukman (2015) indicated that it is the process of putting curriculum into action through an implementation agent (teachers,

principals, education officials, parents among other agents). Only effective curriculum implementation ensures achievement of the objectives for which the curriculum was designed to attain. For effective implementation of curriculum to take place, quality assurance and standards is key. Quality assurance (QA) is one of the most critical tasks facing every nation's educational institutions, so that the societal demands for improved education service delivery would achieve the best learning outcomes that enhance the quality of life of the citizenry (Ayeni, 2010). Quality assurance in education encompasses systematic management, monitoring and evaluation procedures adopted to measure the performance of school administrators (principals), teachers and students against educational objectives to ensure best practices in resource inputs, utilization and curriculum management by the principals to produce students that achieve the set educational goals in secondary schools (Obanya, 2004; Republic of Kenya, 2005). It is mainly conducted by quality assurance and standards officers (QASOs) and headteachers in schools (internal curriculum supervisors). In order to play their role effectively, the QASOs require special skills specific to the job. Supervision of schools is a worldwide phenomenon. Every country having its own policy on how supervision is conducted (Sankale, 2015). It is seen as a democratic action aimed not only at improving classroom instructions but also creating a harmonious environment through continued growth of all concerned; the child, the teacher, the supervisor, the parent and the administration. Britain has the earliest history of supervision (inspection) which took place in 18th and 19th century. The form of supervision was aimed at determining whether the teachers were doing their work the way they were supposed to do failure to which they would be replaced with better teachers immediately. Supervision was a key tool to ensure that all education staff respected the same rules and regulations and followed a similar programme (De Grauwe, 2005). Van Deventer and Kruger (2003) stated that the elements of supervisory roles of principals are; defining the school mission, managing the curriculum and instruction, supervising teaching, monitoring and promoting learner progress. It is important to state that supervision of instruction can only be said to be effective if it achieves its stated objectives, which is quality instructional delivery. Anything to the contrary means the failure of the programme of supervision (Eke & Chinweuba, 2012). This research investigated the influence of instructional supervision on implementation of curriculum in secondary schools in selected North Rift counties; West Pokot, Baringo and Elgeyo-Marakwet, in Kenya.

2. Problem Statement

The performance of secondary school system is influenced by how the quality instructional supervisions activities are done to ensure effective curriculum implementation. The aim of quality assurance and standards is to ensure that curriculum in schools is implemented effectively and meets the emerging needs and challenges. However, in most Kenyan secondary schools including selected North Rift counties; West Pokot, Baringo and Elgeyo-Marakwet in particular have been on academic performance rather than full curriculum implementation (Muriithi, 2012;

Ndaita, 2013; Onzere, 2015). This has seen majority of students joining higher education institutions incapable of competing with the demands of the job market (Wafula, 2010). Utility of quality assurance and standard strategies is key to ensuring curriculum is implemented effectively. However, the focus of most studies has been on external curriculum supervision rather than internal one. This state of affairs motivated the researcher to investigate how instructional supervision processes influenced curriculum supervision in public secondary schools in North Rift counties of Kenya.

3. Purpose of the Study

The purpose of this study was to find out utility of instructional supervision as a quality assurance and standards in curriculum implementation in selected North rift counties of Kenya.

3.1 Research Hypothesis

The paper tests the following null hypothesis:

H₀₁ There is no significant influence of instructional supervision on curriculum implementation in secondary schools

4. Literature Review

4.1 Instructional Supervision and Curriculum Implementation

Supervision is the process of helping, guiding, advising and stimulating growth in subordinate staff in order to improve on the quality of his work (Igbo, 2002). Kochhar (2005) said supervision includes those activities which are primarily and directly concerned with studying and improving the conditions which surround the learning and growth of pupils. Wanzare (2013) refers instructional supervision as quality assurance practice put in place by the QASOs and school administration to monitor the teaching and learning process in the school, and is a way of checking other people's work to ensure that bureaucratic regulations and procedures are followed and that loyalty to the higher authorities is maintained. According to Wanzare (2006), school principals are the chief instructional leaders of their schools whose leadership role is central to establishing and maintaining an effective school. Ayeni (2012) contends that instructional supervision roles performed by supervisors include; monitoring of teachers' attendance during lessons, checking and ensuring adequate preparation of lesson notes, checking and ensuring adequacy of scheme of work and record of work. However, instructional supervision is faced with challenges such as delay in releasing teachers' observation reports, fault-finding mentality during classroom visitation, lack of discussion of lessons with teachers after the visit, laxity in teacher preparation and record keeping, untimed and unstructured teaching notes and incomprehensive schemes of work (Sibanda, Mutopa & Maphosa, 2011). According to Fisher (2011), the schools supervision includes all efforts of school officials directed to provide leadership to the teachers and other educational workers in the improvement of instruction. The

improvement of teaching and learning in schools is the general purpose of supervision. A basic premise of supervision is that a teacher's instructional behaviour affects student learning. An examination of instructional behaviours can lead to improvement in teaching and learning. The effective school research identifies schooling practice and characteristics associated with measurable improvements in student achievement and excellence among student achievement.

The effective improvement of instructional delivery and maintenance of standards in the school system are enhanced through regular internal and external supervision. According to Ayodele (2002), secondary schools are presently supervised by two categories of people, viz: (i) internal supervisors- those within-the school, such as principals, vice-principals and heads of departments: (ii) external supervisors- those outside the school, supervisors as the formally designated officials from the inspectorate division of the Ministry of Education and the various area or Zonal Education Offices. A supervisor could also be the principal of a school, or a senior member of staff of a school (Ani, 2007). However, supervision in a school system implies the process of ensuring that policies, principles, rules, regulations and methods prescribed for purposes of implementing and achieving the objectives for education are effectively carried out (Yuguda & Jailani, 2014). Wanjugu (2011) suggests that head teachers carry out instructional supervision to ensure quality teaching and learning. This means that, the head teacher's role as supervisor is making effort to improve instruction by restructuring of personnel in teaching. A head teacher is the internal supervisor of instructions of his or her school.

4.2 Empirical Review of Studies on Instructional Supervision and Curriculum Implementation

Yuguda and Jailani (2014) assess the general roles of school supervisors in improving teaching quality and effectiveness of schools supervisions. They suggested that supervisors as catalysts should facilitate the implementation of the various sets of roles which will improve the teaching-learning situation in the input-process. This was geared towards an effective, viable, vibrant and qualitative educational system. Hence, the supervisor must seek for genuine cooperation and concern, positive and acceptable disposition among the teachers and their subordinates. Muhammed (2014) study sought to examine principals' administrative process strategies for the achievement of quality assurance in secondary schools in Kogi State. The design of the study was a descriptive survey. The population of the study comprised 228 respondents. The sample of the study consisted of 228 principals. Findings of the study indicated that the principals' planning strategies for quality assurance in secondary schools include preparation of school timetable on time among others. The study concluded that proper use of the documented planning, organizing, coordinating, staff personnel, and budgeting strategies by school principals could promote quality assurance in secondary school administration. Ndebele (2013) study set out to identify supervisory styles prevalent in Bulilima district in Zimbabwe, solicit teachers' views on the supervisory styles and find ways of reconciling teacher-supervisor differences. The sample comprised twenty

primary school teachers and ten school heads. The research used the descriptive survey design and a semi structured questionnaire with both closed questions, where they chose from a set of predetermined responses and open ended questions for data collection. The study showed that supervision offered lacked relevance to instructional improvement. Teachers also felt that supervision offered lacked meaningful feedback. Sibanda *et al.*, (2011) investigated primary school teachers' perceptions on the way school heads undertook lesson observations in selected Zimbabwean primary schools. A qualitative survey design was used. A semi-structured questionnaire was used to collect the data. Sixty-five purposefully selected qualified teachers participated in the study. The study revealed that perceptions of teachers about lesson observations by their heads were largely negative as heads tended to base their lesson observations on the dominant models of supervision. There were few exceptions where teachers' perceptions revealed clinical and collaborative supervisory practices in lesson observation.

In Tanzania, Simbano (2015) study determined the- influence of heads of schools supervisory' practices on teachers' work performance. This study used descriptive design. Target population of the study comprised all 25 head of schools and 822 teachers in public secondary schools in Arusha municipality. The study findings revealed that majority of teachers had negative attitudes towards supervision. Findings indicated that majority of head teachers strongly agreed that supervision benefits teachers on improving their teaching within the classroom and reduces lesson absence by teachers. The major challenges facing head teachers in supervisory practices were overload work by teachers and lack of certain teaching/learning materials averts effective instructional supervision process. In Kenya, Musungu and Nasongo (2008) investigated the instructional role of the head teacher in academic achievement in Kenya Certificate of Secondary Education (KCSE) examinations in Vihiga County. All the 44 head teachers of the selected schools formed part of the sample for the study together with eight teachers from each school sampled randomly. The findings of the study showed that head teachers' instructional role included regular checking of teachers' professional records, regular class supervision, and management plan for carrying out curriculum goals. Further. Mobegi, Ondigi and Oburu (2010) investigated the strategies employed by head teachers and the challenges head teachers had faced in their attempts to provide quality education. The research design used was descriptive survey method. The study population consisted of 120 public secondary schools. The findings of the study showed that head teachers' curriculum supervisory methods were limited to checking of teachers' professional records and gave less emphasize to departmental supervision, self-appraisal and class-visits. Financial constraint was revealed as the major challenge that influenced negatively on physical facilities, teaching and learning materials, and teaching methods.

Wanzare (2012) in a study regarding instructional supervision practices and procedures in secondary schools in Kenya revealed that teachers studied, in general, perceived that some instructional supervisors often used classroom observations as occasions for parading teachers' short-comings and as fault-finding exercises aimed at

catching teachers on the wrong and, as a result, teachers did not benefit from classroom observations. Irungu (2013) study sought to determine the influence of head teachers' instructional supervisory role on pupils' performance in KCPE in Kahuro District. The target population for the study was the head teachers and teachers in all primary schools in the district and the District Quality Assurance and Standards Officer. The study found out that the head teachers rarely engaged in class observation visits. All the head teachers confirmed that teachers in their schools prepared lesson plans. The teachers equally confirmed that the head teachers supervised and observed the activity of lesson plan preparation in their schools. The head teachers confirmed that they assessed pupils' notebooks regularly. The responses by the head teachers showed that most of them deemed the teaching and learning materials provision for the schools as inadequate. Amwayi and Wanjala (2015) investigated the factors that affected performance, the quality monitoring mechanisms in use and mitigation measures for public secondary schools in the two Sub-counties. The study population was 12 principals from Kakamega East, 10 principals from Kakamega Central and two Sub-County Quality Assurance Officers. There was no significant difference between the two sub counties on document review methods. The frequencies of school visits by QASO were irregular as their work was constrained by poor road network, shortage of personnel and financial challenges. Ayeni (2012) study identified the nature of principals' supervisory roles and the perceived effectiveness of principals in the supervision of teachers' instructional tasks. The results showed that most principals accorded desired attention to monitoring of teachers' attendance, preparation of lesson notes and adequacy of diaries of work while tasks such as the provision of instructional materials, reference books, feedback and review of activities with stakeholders were least performed by many principals in secondary schools. The study concluded that challenges that principals faced in the tasks of institutional governance, resource inputs, curriculum delivery and students learning require effective collaboration and goal-oriented synergetic interrelationship between the school and the relevant stakeholders in its environment.

Oduma (2013) paper dealt on quality assurance in Nigeria education system, with specific focus on school managers, teachers and students in the school system. The paper acknowledged that the main policy objective in education in Nigeria is to raise the quality of education at all levels in order to make the recipients of the system more useful to themselves and the society as well. Quality assurance in Nigeria education system is a goal to which learners, teachers, staff and school administration aspires to attain. Among the strategies pointed out, include curriculum review, monitoring and instructional supervision, establishment and compliance to benchmark minimum academic standard among others. Chepkuto (2012) established that roles of QASO include visiting schools regularly and assist greatly in organizing workshops on teaching methods, giving advice and ideas on ways of ensuring implementing curriculum was fully done and by updating teachers on changes in curriculum, preparation of schemes of work, correcting pupils' work and other professional staff in all administration levels. He also noted that teachers benefited from QASOs in

development of schemes of work, lesson plans and records of work and ability to maintain quality instructional materials. It also established that teachers could implement the curriculum in stressing syllabus coverage in time, preparation of teaching learning materials, assessment of pupils work and mobilizing other stakeholders for support towards education. Gichobi (2012) study sought to assess the role of head teachers in curriculum and instruction management of secondary schools in Gatundu. The study used descriptive survey design. The target population of the study comprised of all the 59 head teachers, 237 HODs and 460 teachers from the 59 secondary school. The study established that most of the head teachers were rarely or never engaged in their roles on curriculum and instruction. It was also established that teaching and learning resources in schools were available in schools but they were not adequate. This affected implementation of the curriculum in schools which as a result affected students' performance. A study by Murithi (2012), on influence of head teachers instructional supervision strategies on curriculum implementation in public primary schools established that instructional supervision helps improve head teachers and teachers performance which in turn leads to curriculum implementation. It also concluded that assessment of syllabus coverage by head teachers too lead to curriculum implementation. It also established that instructional supervision enhances head teacher frequency of checking teacher's records on curriculum implementation.

A study by Musungu and Nasongo (2008) established that 8% of the principals in high performing school checked lesson books, schemes of work, register of schools attendance and class attendance registers. Effective principals are perceived as those who are involved in proper tuition and revision. Through supervision of teachers and students work by proper policy, syllabus coverage proper testing, instruction, orientation for new employees and team work building, performance is enhanced. Nzile (2012) investigated the role head teachers play in instructional supervision in order to improve on students' academic achievement in Kitui District secondary schools, as it is perceived by their teachers. The sample consisted of 120 respondents consisting of 60 Heads of Departments and 60 class teachers who were randomly selected from 6 high performing school and 6 low performing schools. About 62.6% of the teachers agreed that head teachers communicated confidently and provided necessary resources for learning. One of the strategies the head teachers employed as perceived by 69.7% teachers was eradicating cheating in examination among the students to a very high extent. About 97.0% of the teachers said there was failure of syllabus coverage. Mwelu (2013) investigated the influence of Quality Assurance and Standards officers' instructional supervision practices on curriculum implementation in public primary schools in Central division, Machakos district, Kenya. Study findings revealed that QASOs monitored how teachers observed time in every subject they handled and how they kept time planning how to carry out instruction in classroom. QASOs are supposed to ensure that all parts of lesson plan takes the time allocated for each part effectively. Majority of the teachers (62.4%) indicated that they had never been supervised by QASO in their instructional process; QASOs stated that they only visited schools once per term. Njiru (2014) assessed the level of resource utilization in primary

schools in Gatundu North District of Kiambu County. The study adopted a descriptive survey design and utilized both qualitative and quantitative approaches. The target population of the study was 58 public primary schools in Gatundu North District. Findings revealed that from 2006 to 2011, almost all the schools in the district had been performing below average. It was also revealed that some physical facilities and other strategic resources needed to support learning activities were lacking. The study also established that learning materials especially books were not adequate in the schools. Teachers prepared curriculum documents but most of them did not use teaching aids regularly.

Sankale (2015) study sought to determine the influence of head teachers' instructional supervisory role on pupils' performance in KCPE in Ololulunga Division. The target population for the study was the 70 head teachers, 480 teachers and 960 pupils in all primary schools in the division totalling 1,510. The study found out that the head teachers rarely engaged in class observation visits. All the head teachers confirmed that teachers in their schools prepared lesson plans. The teachers equally confirmed that the head teachers supervised and observed the activity of lesson plan preparation in their schools. The head teachers confirmed that they assessed pupils' notebooks regularly. The responses by the head teachers showed that most of them deemed the teaching and learning materials provision for the schools as inadequate. Wambui (2015) investigated the influence of head teachers' instructional supervision on pupils' performance in primary schools in Kiambu Sub County, Kenya. The study used descriptive survey research design whose purpose was to describe the state of affairs and involves a method of collecting data by interviewing or administering questionnaires to a sample of individuals. From the study 15 of the head teachers did not sit in class as teaching process went on, they did not check teachers' records of work and check pupils' exercise books. Teaching and learning resources were inadequate for effective learning. Teachers are to be encouraged to prepare records of work and other professional document to have effective teaching. Head teachers (15) indicated that they had not undergone any training before appointment. Head teachers had a lot of workload to accomplish their duties hence they have no time to supervise pupils work. Ngipuo (2015) investigated the influence of Head teachers' instructional supervision practices such as frequent classroom visits, checking of records and provision of teaching and learning resources on pupils' performance in Kenya Certificate of Primary Education in Kakuma refugee Camp. The sample consisted of 20 primary schools, 20 Head teachers and 326 teachers. The instruments for this study were questionnaires for the teachers and interview guide for head teachers. The study findings revealed that the Head teachers' instructional supervision practices influenced pupils' performance in KCPE through head teachers' frequent classroom visits, checking of records and provision of teaching and learning resources.

4.3 Conceptual framework

The conceptual framework for this paper illustrates the relationship between dependent and independent variable. Figure 1.1 shows the model.

5. Materials and Methods

The research adopted a descriptive survey research design. The study was done in selected North Rift counties; West Pokot, Baringo and Elgeyo-Marakwet, Kenya. The counties border Turkana County to the north, Nakuru County to the South, Samburu County to the north East, Trans-Nzoia to the North West, Uasin Gishu to the South West and Kericho County to the South. All the 349 public secondary schools of selected North Rift counties; West Pokot, Baringo and Elgeyo-Marakwet, 14 sub county quality assurance and standards officers (SC-QAS), 349 principals and all the teachers of the county public secondary schools, were the target population of the study. Stratified random sampling technique was used to select 35 out of the 349 (10%) of secondary schools in the region. This study utilised questionnaires and interview schedules as the research instruments for data collection. The data collected for this study was analysed using quantitative and qualitative approaches. Quantitative data collected was analysed using descriptive and inferential statistics. Qualitative data from interviews were analysed using thematic analysis.

6. Results and Discussions

Instructional supervision is concerned with supporting and assisting teachers to improve instructions through changing their behavior (Ngipuo, 2015). The first objective of the study was to determine how instructional supervision influenced curriculum implementation in secondary schools in North Rift Counties Kenya. The teachers were asked to indicate the frequency to which instructional supervision was conducted in their schools as; never (1), rarely (2), sometimes (3), occasionally (4) and always (5). The results are presented in Table 4.1.

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Table 1: Instructional Supervision Processes in Schools

Statement	Never	Rarely	Sometimes	Occasionally	Always	Mean	SD
i. Principal finds out whether teachers follow schemes of work	2 (0.6%)	11 (3.3%)	41 (12.2%)	114 (34.0%)	167 (49.9%)	4.2925	.85003
ii. Principal communicates with the teachers about instructional concern	1 (0.3%)	5 (1.5%)	34 (10.1%)	91 (27.2%)	204 (60.9%)	4.4687	.76099
iii. Principal provides timely constructive and objective feedback after classroom observation	5 (1.5%)	23 (6.9%)	61 (18.2%)	131 (39.1%)	115 (34.3%)	3.9791	.96783
iv. Principal demonstrates teaching techniques to teachers on delivery of content	21 (6.3%)	46 (13.7%)	89 (26.6%)	92 (27.5%)	87 (26.0%)	3.5313	1.19307
v. Principal ensures teachers make good use of instructional time to complete the syllabus before exams	0 (0%)	9 (2.7%)	23 (6.9%)	75 (22.4%)	228 (68.1%)	4.5582	.73943
vi. Principal offers useful teaching suggestions to enhance syllabus coverage	3 (0.9%)	17 (5.1%)	45 (13.4%)	101 (30.1%)	169 (50.4%)	4.2418	.93087
vii. Principal ensures that teachers have adequate teaching-learning materials to complete the syllabus	0 (0%)	8 (2.4%)	26 (7.8%)	55 (16.4%)	246 (73.4%)	4.6090	.73365
Composite scores						4.2401	0.88227

The results show that half 167 (49.9%) of teachers indicated that their head teachers always found out whether they followed schemes of work when teaching. The results also show that 114 (34.0%) of teachers said that this happened often in their schools. computed mean (M=4.29) and standard deviation scores (SD=0.85) suggests that most head teachers in schools regularly ensures that teachers utilise schemes of work while teaching to ensure curriculum implementation was conducted well. The result was different from Gichobi (2012) research in Kiambu that found out that 39.5% of teachers felt that school heads often checked records and schemes of work and always encouraged effective use of academic time. In addition, Irungu (2013) professional documents preparation was enforced and adhered to and that assessment of learners' notebooks was done regularly. In contrast to the study findings, Sankale (2015) research in Narok found out that half of head teachers checked teachers' professional records weekly while no head teacher responded that they checked teachers' professional records daily. This implied that the head teachers did not check and approve teachers' schemes of work hence it could affect curriculum implementation. The usage of scheme of work is an internal quality assurance process that ensures that the syllabus is implemented throughout the academic year. To support this assumption, Watsulu and

Simatwa (2011) explain that scrutiny of schemes of work is an important role that internal curriculum supervisors perform to enhance quality curriculum implementation.

Secondly, most 204 (60.9%) of respondents agreed that their school principals always communicated with them on instructional issues. The descriptive results suggest that respondents tended to have a common opinion on this statement ($M=4.46$ and $SD=0.76$). The result implies that it is the duty of head teachers to regularly find out and talk with teachers with regard to how instructional process is conducted in schools as it would improve the curriculum implementation process. The study coincides with Gichobi (2012) research in Gatundu that found out that schools heads were discussing issues on curriculum instructions with staff during the staff meetings. Majority of the head teacher reported that they always organized meetings and involved teachers in making school programmes. Wanzare (2013) informs that in an apparent recognition of the centrality of communication in the head teacher's supervisory role, the Kenya Education Management Institute (KEMI), established in Kenya mainly to provide induction courses in management skills to educational managers, such as head teachers, and has incorporated communication into its course content as a tool of management. Thirdly, when asked as to whether their school principal provided timely, constructive and objective feedback as a result of classroom observation, 23 (6.9%) said they often gave, 61 (18.2%) said that they sometimes provided, 131 (39.1%) said that they occasionally gave while 115 (34.3%) indicated that they always give. The result shows that most head teachers occasionally ($M=3.97$ and $SD=0.96$) gave constructive feedback to teachers on how to improve their instructional process after observing them in class. This implied that head teachers performed their work objectively without favour or ill intentions of advising teachers when observing their teaching and learning processes in the classrooms. Similarly to the study findings, principals in Wanzare (2013) study did not seem to regard holding conferences with teachers, especially after classroom observation, as an important component of head teachers' instructional supervisory role and, consequently, their perceptions regarding this supervision practice were largely negative. Perhaps, in instances where instructional supervisors held post-observation conferences with teachers, they were dominated by the instructional supervisors themselves, with no tangible input from teachers observed. In contrast to the study findings, Irungu (2013) established that head teachers' engagement in class observation visits was infrequent hence affecting quality assurance in schools.

The results also showed that 46 (13.7%) of teachers indicating that their school heads rarely demonstrated teaching methods on how to deliver curriculum content. However, 89 (26.6%) said that they sometimes demonstrated to them, 92 (27.5%) said that they occasionally did that and only 87 (26.0%) indicated that they always provided demonstrations to teachers on how to improve their classroom curriculum delivery process. The mean statistics show that teachers said that head teachers occasionally demonstrated teaching techniques on how to deliver classroom content but standard deviation scores ($SD=1.19$) suggested that some head teachers did not while others did. In relation to the study findings, Ndaita (2013) established that most secondary school

principals in Kitui West Sub County provided opportunities in order to enhance effective application of pedagogical skills in classroom situation. In addition, Mburu (2016) found out that majority of the head teachers, 73%, sometimes or always ensure employment of right methods of teaching. Employment of the right methods of teaching and learning is important in improving content delivery and increasing pupil understanding in relation to what is taught during the lesson. Content delivery involves use of teaching aids. As internal curriculum supervisors, head teachers are supposed to advise teachers on how to improve their instructional methods for effective curriculum implementation in the classroom. The findings also revealed that majority 228 (68.1%) of teachers agreed that their head teachers always ensured that they made good use of instructional time to enhance syllabus coverage and allow adequate time for examinations revision. The descriptive scores show that the respondents agreed with the statement ($M=4.55$ and $SD=0.73$). This means that in most schools, head teachers ensured that teachers attended their classes thereby ensuring that school syllabus was covered on time providing adequate opportunity for students to revise for examinations. When there is no time wastage, curriculum implementation process would be conducted efficiently and effectively. In agreement with the study findings, Ndaita (2013) established that most teachers (74.1%) indicated that constant monitoring of teachers in the learning process was one of the major roles that the principals applied in enhancing effective application of pedagogical skills in classroom situation. In agreement with this study, Mburu (2016), 47% of the total head teachers completely manage classroom routines and procedures effectively without loss of instructional time. This means that a large number of head teachers completely manage classroom routines and procedures effectively without loss of instructional time. They ensured that classroom routine is maintained every day. This involves helping learners understand different subjects taught by their teachers. Ensuring all lessons are taught is important in improving teaching and learning process. Through their managerial process, head teachers ensured that teachers carry out their day to day activities, which included attending all lessons.

When asked on the frequent to which their school heads offered useful teaching suggestions on enhancement of syllabus coverage, 3 (0.9%) indicated they never support, 17 (5.1%) said they rarely offer, 45 (13.4%) said they sometimes offer, 101 (30.1%) indicated that they occasionally offer and 169 (50.4%) said their heads always provided regular support. The result therefore shows that most head teachers occasionally ($M=4.24$ and $SD=0.93$) provide important suggestions to their teachers to ensure effective syllabus coverage hence leading to achievement of curriculum goals in secondary schools. This implies that most head teachers are helping their teachers with critical suggestions on how to navigate through syllabus coverage in schools. The study findings also revealed that most 246 (73.4%) of teachers admitted that their principals always ensured that they had adequate teaching and learning materials for curriculum implementation. The descriptive statistics confirms that the respondents strongly agreed ($M=4.6$ and $SD=0.7$) with the statement that this was a common occurrence in their schools. With adequate instructional materials provision, curriculum

implementation becomes easy and therefore learner understanding of subject matter in class is enhanced. This is in agreement with Ndaita (2013) who found out that most principals availed adequate teaching and learning resources in the school in order to enhance effective application of pedagogical skills in a classroom situation. In addition, Gichobi (2012) result showed that teaching and learning resources in schools were available in schools but they were not adequate. Similarly, Irungu (2013) found out that teaching and learning materials were deemed to be inadequate by many head teachers in their schools. This affected effective implementation of the curriculum in schools which as a result affected students' performance. There can be no effective supervision of instruction without instructional materials.

The result also suggests that provision of adequate instructional learning materials is a core function that principals in secondary schools are putting their energy on to ensure effective curriculum implementation. Composite average statistics shows that instructional supervision was occasionally done ($M=4.24$ and $SD=0.88$) by majority of principals in secondary schools in West Pokot, Baringo and Elgeyo-Marakwet Counties. In line with the study findings, Gichobi (2012) research found out that most head teachers partially engaged in curriculum and instruction practices. Similarly in Kisii County, Mobegi et al (2010) found out that head teachers employed inadequate methods for the supervision of teachers in the sampled schools, preferring to rely on written records to establish the quality of education. To check on the relationship between instructional supervision and curriculum implementation, composite scores were correlated and results are presented in Table 4.2.

Table 2: Relationship between Instructional Supervision and Curriculum Implementation

		Instructional supervision	Curriculum implementation
Instructional supervision	Pearson Correlation	1	.491**
	Sig. (2-tailed)		.000
	N	335	335
Curriculum implementation	Pearson Correlation	.491**	1
	Sig. (2-tailed)	.000	
	N	335	335

** . Correlation is significant at the 0.01 level (2-tailed).

According to Table 2, there exist significant positive relationship ($r=0.491$ and $p=0.001$) between instructional supervision by head teachers and curriculum implementation process in secondary schools in selected North Rift counties, Kenya. The statistics suggest that continuous instructional supervision processes by head teachers; there is likelihood of curriculum implementation process being conducted well in secondary schools. In agreement with this study, Onzere (2015) established that instructional supervision in classrooms ensured efficiency and effective implementation of curriculum which was a key indicator of academic performance of schools. Similarly, Ndaita (2013) found out that majority of teachers, 66.7% indicated that their principals' instructional supervision influenced their academic performance in the school to a greater extent. Even in Kakuma, Ngipuo (2015) found out that instructional supervision

practices influences learners performance in examinations through head teachers' frequent classroom visits, checking of records, provision of teaching and learning resources, teachers' perception on the head teachers' instructional supervision techniques and challenges experienced by head teachers in conducting instructional supervision. The result from other studies confirms that effective curriculum implementation process is dependent on whether instructional supervision is effectively conducted by internal curriculum supervisors in schools. Further, the teachers through open-ended questions were asked to state how instructional supervision procedures influenced curriculum implementation in their schools. Their feedback is presented in Table 3.

Table 3: Respondents perceptions on the influence of instructional supervision on curriculum implementation

Instructional supervision influence	Frequency	Percent
Fair / average / moderate	63	18.8
Good – ensures objectives are attained	59	17.6
Instructional materials are up to date as head teachers work together with teachers	58	17.3
Ensures smooth teaching and learning process	57	17.0
It helps to improve on results	17	5.1
More needs to be done	17	5.1
To be given attention by the principals	14	4.2
So demanding	11	3.3
Ensure adequate instructional resources are provided	1	.3
None response	38	11.3
Total	335	100.0

According to 63 (18.8%) of teachers, instructional supervision process has had moderate effect on curriculum implementation in their schools. In addition, 59 (17.6%) indicated that it is significant as it ensures that the objectives of the schools are attained, 58 (17.3%) of teachers indicted that it ensures that right and proper instructional learning materials are availed and 57 (17.0%) indicted that it ensures that there is smooth teaching and learning process that is critical to improved academic attainment by students in secondary schools. The above responses show that teachers have positive perceptions on the influence of instructional supervision on curriculum implementation in public secondary schools in the three counties under study. In agreement with this study, Musungu and Nasongo (2008) established that effective supervision of teachers is necessary if they are to remain productive. Influencing is a key process in supervision. It is almost impossible to work with people towards a common goal by use of force or coercion. The head-teacher would therefore need to know how to establish good working relationships with the teachers in the school. In addition, Ngipuo (2015) established that the teachers perceived the head teachers' instructional supervision techniques positively because they further co-operation and teamwork among staff members. Thus, the principals' instructional supervision techniques are beneficial to the teachers when implementing the curriculum.

6.1 Principals Views on Instructional Supervision Effect on Curriculum Implementation

The study also sought views from school head teachers on how instructional supervision influenced curriculum implementation in schools. Principal No. 1 from one school in Marakwet West Sub County had this to say:

Continuous monitoring of teaching and learning through: (a) signing in and out, (b) lesson attendance forms, (c) alignment, (4) rescheduling timetable and checking students' progress.

In agreement with study findings, Ngipuo (2015) research found out that classroom visits enabled monitoring of classroom activities; class records guide teaching and enable intervention; while teaching and learning resources improve pupils' learning experience and outcomes. Another principal No. 13 from Baringo Central Sub County had a different opinion with regards on how instructional supervisions happen in their school by indicating that:

It is inevitable since things are done when thoroughly supervised by a senior officer. However, it is largely dependent on the supervisor for it to be implemented effectively.

While sharing similar sentiments with Principal No. 1, another principal (No. 26 from West Pokot County had this to say:

Monitoring of various activities in the school like lesson attendance, inspecting/checking of required documents like schemes of work, lesson plans and lesson notes.

The responses made by head teachers suggest that instructional supervision actually happens in schools. The headteachers also reported that to ensure effective teaching and learning process in school, the schools improvise available resources and also ensured there is provision of more resources purchased through school fees and government funds. In agreement with these findings, Sankale (2015) found out that headteachers' engagement in class observation visits was infrequent; checking of professional records; and that assessment of pupils' notebooks was done irregularly. The principals said that instructional supervision helped in effective curriculum implementation. This is because instructional tasks are done and syllabus is covered as per scheduled time. The head teachers are gives directions, rules, regulations concerning given duties and also ensuring that curriculum is implemented. In agreement with this study finding, Watsulu and Simatwa (2011) asserted that professional documents assessments assist to guide teachers in preparation of content, delivery skills and required learning resources for quality education provision. This implies that when a head teachers knows the strengths and weaknesses of teachers and build on their strengths and weaknesses and give them support and proper feedback,

then teachers work much better to improve their instruction hence effective curriculum implementation.

6.2 Quality Assurance Officers Response on Instructional Supervision

The researcher also sought perceptions that QASOs had with regard to how instructional supervision influenced curriculum implementation. This is what SC-QASO No. 10 had this to say:

It enables teachers to undertake their duties diligently in an effort to achieve objectives outlined in the course of their teaching.

Secondly, SC-QASO No. 11 indicated that:

Taken positively, it will improve curriculum delivery. However, some few individuals take it negatively citing equal rank with supervisors.

This implies that some teachers do not embrace the idea of instructional supervision by looking down on their supervisors. This behaviour may affect the achievement of curriculum goals and objectives. In agreement with the study, Simbano (2015) found out that teachers had negative attitudes towards instructional supervision by headteachers. This implies that instructional supervision may positively or negatively affect the quality of curriculum implementation in schools. Still on another issue, SC-QASO No. 3 mentioned the following with regard to instructional supervision process happening in schools:

Instructional supervision has been done moderately due to challenge pertaining mobility. It has though influenced curriculum implementation in schools that are equipped.

On a positive note, SC-QASO No. 2 observed that:

It is a good idea as the teacher is assured to know his/her strength and weakness during instruction process and how to improve them.

From the responses given by education officers, instructional supervision is aimed to ensure that quality education is provided in secondary schools although an issue of contention is that all stakeholders should agree and have a common opinion for it to succeed. Ahmad (2011) argues that majority of the heads' emphasis was on knowing the strengths and weaknesses of teachers and provision of feedback for instructional improvement because they thought that provision of proper feedback to teachers can improve their instruction. Therefore, quality instructional supervision processes guarantee quality curriculum implementation. This enhances quality of education as evidenced in high academic achievements by students in examinations.

7. Conclusions and Recommendations

Supervision has been found to be an indispensable aspect in teaching and learning towards achievement of school objectives. Research findings showed that as part of instructional supervision, most principals always ensured that teaching and learning materials were available for classroom instructions in schools. This showed that most secondary school principals valued the importance of providing teachers with adequate instructional resources to facilitate effective curriculum implementation. Also as part of instructional supervision, the study established that majority of the school principals regularly ensured that they communicated with teachers so that they could provide them with support in case they needed to facilitate the curriculum implementation in school. The results also showed that as an internal quality assurance and standard practice, principals occasionally checked on teachers' schemes of work, offered suggestions on syllabus coverage, provided timely feedback on classroom observation and assisted teacher in teaching strategies and demonstrations. Composite scores showed that the process of instructional supervision was conducted on regular occasions in all public secondary schools in the county. Further, Karl Pearson correlation coefficient statistics showed that the relationship between internal instructional supervision was positive. The null hypothesis was also rejected leading to the deduction that there was significant influence of instructional supervision towards curriculum implementation in secondary schools in the selected three north rift counties. This implied that the process of supervision as an internal quality assurance process, aimed at assisting teachers to become better through enhancing their capacity to deliver quality teaching and learning process to students. To improve on instructional supervision, there is need for principals to continuously work with teachers on how to improve and revolutionise their teaching and learning approaches to match with the current and global trends in the teaching profession. There is need for a balance to be arrived at in instructional supervision so that teachers would not see that they are harassed by principals who conduct these supervision with 'boss' mentality hence affecting teacher morale in delivering classroom instruction.

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